

AXIAL COMPRESSIVE PROPERTIES OF RANDOMLY DISTRIBUTED DISCONTINUOUS LONG-CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Planar randomly fiber reinforced composites are of interest in certain structural applications because they have some advantages: (1) they can provide stiffness and strength for multiple load directions; (2) they have ease of fabrication of complex components. The use of randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP has the potential to lead to significant cost savings over continuous CFRP or CFRTP as automated manufacturing methods can be more easily employed. Moreover, high levels of automation lead to more consistent part quality and reduced cycle times, therefore lending these composites to high volume manufacture processes. Mechanical characterizations of random composites are required to design structural components from these materials. The potential of the randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP has not been fully recognized in the fiber composite technology community as yet. In the present study, the axial compressive properties of the randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP were investigated. The stress-strain curve shows large non-linear behaviour. The axial compressive modulus of 24.9 (in-plane) and 9.7 (through-thickness) GPa. The axial compressive strength was 211 (in-plane), and 144 (through-thickness) MPa. The results clearly indicate that there are large scattering of axial compressive modulus and strength. The failure morphology for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions is significantly different. The specimens oriented in-plane directions show cracks propagating through the kinking of the load-aligned tows and matrix cracking (delamination or splitting). The specimens oriented through-thickness directions show the deformation mode with plies extruding out of the free surfaces of the specimen perpendicular to the fiber direction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Increasing interest has grown for carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites (CFRTP) due to reduced cycle times, opening up possibilities for high volume manufacture. Moreover, CFRTP exhibit higher chemical resistance and impact properties over conventional carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting matrix composites (CFRP) [1].

Planar randomly fiber reinforced composites are of interest in certain structural applications because they have some advantages: (1) they can provide stiffness and strength for multiple load directions; (2) they have ease of fabrication of complex components.

The use of randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP has the potential to lead to significant cost savings over continuous CFRP or CFRTP as automated manufacturing methods can be more easily employed. Moreover, high levels of automation lead to more consistent part quality and reduced cycle times, therefore lending these composites to high volume manufacture processes [2].

Mechanical characterizations of random composites are required to design structural components from these materials. The potential of the randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP has not been fully recognized in the fiber composite technology community as yet.

In the present work, axial compressive properties and fracture behavior of the randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP were investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

The novel randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP thick plate has been developed by the Komatsu Matere Co.,Ltd..

The carbon fiber is made of TRH60 polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fiber (TRH60 60M, Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation), which has a diameter of $d_f = 6.13 \mu\text{m}$ as a bundle of 60000 filaments. The thermoplastic epoxy is made of difunctional epoxy resin and difunctional phenolic compound mixed at a stoichiometric ratio ($\text{XNR6850V/XNH6850V} = 100/6.5$) (Nagase ChemteX Corporation) [3].

Dry carbon fiber bundle was immersed in methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) solvent solution of the thermoplastic epoxy and then dried in an oven at 150°C . The discontinuous long-fiber chip was a fiber length of 50 mm and was obtained from the thermoplastic epoxy impregnated cut carbon fiber bundles. The chip was strewed in the metal mold in-plane randomly and the random CFRTP plate ($200 \times 200 \times 25$ mm) was fabricated using a vacuum hot pressing method at the temperature of 240°C and the external presser of 8 MPa.

2.2 Specimen Preparation

The random CFRTP plate were cut into rectangular axial compressive test specimens in several position with dimensions of 15 mm in length (L), 10 mm in width (W) and 10 mm in thickness (T). The axis in the specimen was oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions.

2.3 Density Measurement

The densities of all rectangular specimens (ρ_c) ($10 \times 10 \times 15$ mm) were measured via ethanol immersion (ASTM D792) [4]. The densities of carbon fiber (ρ_f) and matrix (ρ_m) are 1.81 g/cm^3 and 1.20 g/cm^3 .

2.4 Axial Compressive Test

The axial compressive test gives a load, P as a function of extension, U curve up to failure. Axial compressive stress (σ_c) and axial compressive strain (ε_c) were calculated as follows:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P}{WT} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_c = \frac{U - C_S P}{L} \quad (2)$$

where, C_S is a system compliance.

All tests were conducted in the laboratory environment at room temperature. Crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min was applied. The axial compressive modulus is calculated using a least square method for the straight line section of stress-strain curve.

After testing, the surface views of fracture were examined using a digital microscope (DM) (VHX-6000 and VH-ZST, Keyence Corporation).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Density

Figure 1 shows the density distribution of the random CFRTP plate measured using rectangular specimens with ethanol immersion method.

Figure 1: Density distribution of the random CFRTTP plate measured using rectangular specimens with ethanol immersion method.

The density difference of the random CFRTTP plate was very small, although the localized density difference was observed due to localized heating and external pressure conditions during fabrication. The densities, ρ_C of all rectangular specimens were determined to be 1.465 – 1.511 g/cm³ (ADV: average 1.485 g/cm³, SD: standard deviation 0.011 g/cm³).

3.2 Axial Compressive Property

Figure 2 shows the positions of axial compressive test specimens.

Figure 2: Positions of axial compressive test specimens.

It was arranged so that the axial compressive property distributions for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions might be obtained.

Typical axial compressive stress-strain (σ_C - ϵ_C) curves for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Typical axial compressive stress-strain curves for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions.

The axial compressive stress-strain curve of the specimen oriented in-plane direction shows a large non-linear behavior and complicated shape. By the axial carbon fibers, the specimen shows the intermediate modulus in the initial stage of loading (this modulus was defined as axial compressive modulus, E_C). Subsequently, when the vertical cracks were occurred (this strength was defined as fracture strength, σ_{CC}), the stress was dropped quickly and the specimen continues to endure stress without instantaneous failure.

On the other hand, the axial compressive stress-strain curve of the specimen oriented through-thickness direction shows a large non-linear behavior. The specimen shows the low modulus in the initial stage of loading (this modulus was defined as axial compressive modulus, E_C). Subsequently, the slope $d\sigma_C/d\varepsilon_C$ decreased slightly and the specimen continues to endure stress without instantaneous failure. The axial compressive stress at which these tangent lines intersect is defined as the axial compressive strength, σ_{CC} .

Figure 4 shows the axial compressive property (axial compressive modulus, E_C and strength, σ_{CC}) distributions for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions.

(a) modulus, E_C (in-plane).

(b) modulus, E_C (through-thickness).

Figure 4: Axial compressive property distributions for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions.

Axial compressive modulus and strength in in-plane direction were higher than those in through-thickness direction. The axial compressive modulus is higher, leading to a higher axial compressive strength. There exists a relationship between the axial compressive modulus and strength. However, there is no clear relationship between the axial compressive properties (modulus and strength) and density.

The average and standard deviation axial compressive modulus was found to be 24.9 (8.6) (in-plane) and 9.7 (1.6) (through-thickness) GPa. The average and standard deviation axial compressive strength was found to be 211 (46) (in-plane) and 144 (31) (through-thickness) MPa. The results clearly indicate that there are large scattering of axial compressive modulus and strength.

Figure 5 shows typical axial compressive fracture surfaces for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness.

(a) in-plane.

(b) through-thickness.

Figure 5: Typical fracture surfaces for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions.

The failure morphology for the specimens oriented in-plane and through-thickness directions is significantly different. The specimens oriented in-plane directions show cracks propagating through the kinking of the load-aligned tows and matrix cracking (delamination or splitting). The specimens oriented through-thickness directions show the deformation mode with plies extruding out of the free surfaces of the specimen perpendicular to the fiber direction.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results of the axial compressive tests of the randomly distributed discontinuous long-CFRTP are summarized as follows:

- (1) The axial compressive stress-strain curve shows large non-linear behavior, with the axial compressive modulus of 24.9 (in-plane) and 9.7 (through-thickness) GPa.
- (2) The axial compressive strength was 211 (in-plane), and 144 (through-thickness) MPa.

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